

Internal Organisation of German Energy Communities – Analysis of Responses to a Questionnaire

Björn Hoops¹

The project “Private Law and the Energy Commons” investigates citizen-led initiatives to produce renewable energy as a group (hereinafter: energy communities) and examines how the laws of the EU and Member States, in particular in Germany and Italy, pose obstacles to their flourishing. The EU Directives 2018/2001 (Renewable Energy Directive) and 2019/944 (Internal Electricity Market Directive) set requirements for the internal organisation of existing energy communities that want to qualify as ‘Renewable Energy Community’ and, respectively, ‘Citizen Energy Community’. These requirements concern the purpose of the organisation, membership, the right to exit, control over the community, and the disbursement of profits. To lay an empirical base for an evaluation of whether the Directives and the laws of Member States pose obstacles to the flourishing of energy communities, I have made a questionnaire to examine how energy communities shape their internal organisation in practice. This document summarises the responses of 127 groups of citizens who together produce renewable energy in Germany.

Methodology

The questionnaire was directed at groups of citizens who together produce renewable energy in Germany and devised on the basis of the organisational aspects covered by the EU Directives: the purpose of the community, membership requirements, requirements for an exit through the cancellation or transfer of shares, voting rights in the general assembly, the appointment or dismissal of the management board / board of directors, the composition of these bodies, decision-making powers of the different bodies, and the disbursement of profits. To make statistical connections between basic decisions of the community and its internal organisation visible, the questionnaire includes questions on the sources of the renewable energy produced, the total RE generation capacity, the community’s year of foundation, its legal form, its sources of funding, donations to good causes and its degree of professionalisation through paid positions.

¹ Björn Hoops holds the Chair of Private Law and Sustainability at the Faculty of Law of the University of Groningen, The Netherlands. From April 2022 to March 2024 he is Marie Curie Fellow at the University of Turin. This empirical research forms part of the project “Private Law and the Energy Commons”, which has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101024836.

The questionnaire was available online for five months, from April to August 2023. It was distributed throughout the networks of several regional associations of cooperatives and national stakeholders. I received 178 responses. I then cleaned data to eliminate substantially incomplete or otherwise unusable responses. Out of 178 responses, 127 responses were used for the statistical analysis. I applied the descriptive statistics tools and correlation analysis tools of SPSS 28 to the data.

94 out of 127 respondents are cooperatives, 23 of the respondents combine a cooperative with a limited partnership with a private limited-liability company (*GmbH & Co. KG*), and one respondent combines a cooperative with a civil law partnership (*GbR*). Nine respondents have a different legal form or combinations thereof. There are 1,750 citizen initiatives in the energy sector,² 877 of which are cooperatives.³ As 70 to 75% of those cooperatives produce energy,⁴ the number of responding cooperatives (118) represents around 18% of the total population of energy-producing cooperatives.

Characteristics of the respondents

The following tables show the sources of the renewable energy generated, total renewable energy capacity per community, how the generated energy is used, the year of foundation of the community, the number of members per community, paid positions within the community, the legal form of the respondent, and their sources of funding.

TYPE OF RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCE (several answers permitted)

Type	Number	Percentage of all respondents (in %)
Biogas	8	6.3
Biomass	22	17.3
Geothermal power generators	0	0
Hydropower generators	10	7.9
Solar panels	104	81.9

² Caramizaru & Uihlein 2020, p. 5.

³ <https://www.dgrv.de/bundesgeschäftsstelle-energiegenossenschaften/#:~:text=Die%20877%20Energiegenossenschaften%20stehen%20mit,die%20breite%20Akzeptanz%20der%20Energiewende> (last accessed on 1 September 2023).

⁴ Ö. Yildiz, J. Rommel, S. Debor, L. Holstenkamp, F. Mey, J.R. Müller, J. Radtke & J. Rognli, 'Renewable energy cooperatives as gatekeepers or facilitators? Recent developments in Germany and a multidisciplinary research agenda', 6 *Energy Research & Social Science* 2015, 59-73, 62.

Wind turbines	49	38.6
Hydrogen	1	0.8

Connections with the source of renewable energy

Correlated	Direction	Correlation Coefficient (Spearman)	p-level
Wind ↔ Renewable energy capacity	Positive	0.49	0.99
Wind ↔ Electricity fed into public grid	Positive	0.268	0.99
Wind ↔ Number of members	Positive	0.29	0.99
Wind ↔ No paid position	Negative	-0.252	0.99
Wind ↔ Day-to-day manager	Positive	0.214	0.95
Wind ↔ Bank loans	Positive	0.206	0.95
PV ↔ Electricity fed into public grid	Positive	0.516	0.99
PV ↔ supply of certain building(s)	Positive	0.514	0.99
PV ↔ Number of members	Positive	0.175	0.95
PV ↔ Equity as founding source	Positive	0.248	0.99
PV ↔ Bank loans as funding source	Negative	-0.482	0.99
PV ↔ subordinated loans from members as funding	Positive	0.23	0.99
Biogas / Biomass ↔ local heating net	Positive	0.299 / 0.649	0.99
Biogas ↔ no paid position	Negative	-0.177	0.95
Biomass ↔ Bank loans as funding source	Positive	0.31	0.99
Hydropower ↔ public heating net	Positive	0.282	0.99
Hydropower ↔ subordinated loans as funding source	Negative	0.202	0.95

The SPSS correlation analysis produces some significant correlations between the source of renewable energy employed by the energy community and other characteristics. The use of wind turbines is in particular positively correlated with a higher generation capacity and number

of members. This appears logical because each wind turbine requires substantially more funding from members or lenders and produces much more energy than, for instance, small-scale PV projects. Also, there seems to be a positive connection between wind turbines and professionalisation, in the form of a significant positive correlation with a paid day-to-day manager and a negative correlation with the respondent having no paid positions. This could hint at the cumbersome management of such a large installation and investment. Concerning the financing of renewable energy projects, there is a significant positive correlation between wind turbines and the use of bank loans, which seems to point to the large investment sum that cannot be covered by the capital provided by the members. Solar power is also positively correlated with a higher number of members. In contrast to wind power, PV projects display a negative correlation with funding from bank loans. There is a positive correlation with the use of equity and subordinated loans from members. This correlation may point to the lower investment sum. As was to be expected, biogas and biomass installations are more likely to feed heat into a local private grid, while PV and wind installations are more likely to feed electricity into the public grid. Biogas installations are more likely to be financed through bank loans. Hydropower is more likely to be fed into public heating systems and less likely to be financed through subordinated loans from members.

TOTAL RENEWABLE ENERGY CAPACITY

Capacity	Number	Percentage (in %)
1-200 kW	18	14.2
201-1.000 kW (0.2-1 MW)	34	26.8
> 1 MW	75	59.1

Connections with renewable energy capacity

Correlated with	Direction	Correlation Coefficient (Spearman)	p-level
Number of members	Positive	0.386	0.99
Day-to-day manager	Positive	0.316	0.99
Paid directors	Positive	0.216	0.95
No paid position	Negative	-0.415	0.99
Equity as funding source	Negative	-0.187	0.95
Bank loans as funding source	Positive	0.28	0.99

The SPSS correlation analysis produces some significant correlations between the generation capacity and other characteristics. There is a positive correlation between a higher generation capacity and a higher number of members as well as professionalisation in the form of day-to-day managers and paid directors. The meaning of these correlations is ambiguous. More members can finance a larger generation capacity, but a larger generation capacity can also accommodate more members. Professionalisation can be a pre-requisite for a larger generation capacity, but the revenue from a larger generation capacity can lay the ground for professionalisation. Another insight is that a higher generation capacity is more likely to be financed through bank loans and less likely to be financed through equity.

DESTINATION OF THE GENERATED ENERGY (several answers permitted)

	Number	Percentage of all respondents (in %)
We feed the electricity into the utility grid.	114	89.8
We supply a specific building/specific buildings with electricity.	74	58.3
We feed the heat into a utility grid.	4	3.1
We feed the heat into a small-scale local grid.	23	18.1

Connections with the use of the generated energy renewable energy capacity

Correlated	Direction	Correlation Coefficient (Spearman)	p-level
Electricity fed into the grid \leftrightarrow Number of members	Positive	0.219	0.95
Electricity fed into the grid \leftrightarrow Use of equity as funding source	Positive	0.195	0.95
Electricity supplied to buildings \leftrightarrow Use of equity as funding source	Positive	0.317	0.99

Electricity fed into the grid / supplied to a building ↔ Use of bank loans	Negative	-0.306 / -0.355	0.99
Heat fed into a local grid ↔ Use of bank loans	Positive	0.3	0.99
Electricity fed into the grid ↔ Subordinated loans	Positive	0.269	0.99

In addition to the correlations already discussed above, the SPSS correlation analysis produces some significant correlations between the destination of the energy and other characteristics. Energy communities that feed their electricity into the public grid appear to have more members and are more likely to use equity and subordinated loans for their renewable energy projects, while they are less likely to use bank loans. As the majority of respondents have PV projects and PV projects are more likely to use equity, while wind projects are less likely to use equity, the use of solar power may be a moderating factor in the choice of the source of funding. By contrast, respondents with a local heat grid are more likely to use bank loans.

YEAR OF FOUNDATION

Statistics

N	Valid	127
Median		2012

		Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulated Percent
Valid	1921	1	,8	,8
	1922	1	,8	1,6
	1985	1	,8	2,4
	1996	1	,8	3,1
	2006	2	1,6	4,7
	2007	1	,8	5,5
	2008	3	2,4	7,9
	2009	10	7,9	15,7
	2010	9	7,1	22,8
	2011	32	25,2	48,0
	2012	24	18,9	66,9

2013	12	9,4	76,4
2014	5	3,9	80,3
2015	7	5,5	85,8
2016	4	3,1	89,0
2017	4	3,1	92,1
2018	3	2,4	94,5
2021	4	3,1	97,6
2022	1	,8	98,4
2023	2	1,6	100,0
Valid	127	100,0	

NUMBER OF MEMBERS

Members	Number	Percentage (in %)
1-20	7	5.5
21-100	25	19.7
101-300	51	40.2
301-1.000	37	29.1
>1.000	7	5.5

Connections with number of members

Correlated	Direction	Correlation Coefficient (Spearman)	p-level
Paid directors	Positive	0.183	0.95
No paid positions	Negative	-0.347	0.99
Use of equity as funding source	Positive	0.212	0.95

In addition to the correlations already discussed above, the SPSS correlation analysis produces some significant correlations between the number of members and other characteristics. Larger energy communities are more likely to have paid directors and less likely to have no paid positions. This seems logical because a greater number of members are more likely to provide the financial resources for paid positions and professionalised organisations are able to accommodate more members.

PAID POSITIONS (PROFESSIONALISATION) (several answers permissible)

Paid?	Number	Percentage of all respondents (in %)
A manager of day-to-day business (if not the directors)	41	32.3
(The Board of) Directors	23	18.1
The Supervisory Board	4	3.1
None	59	46.5

Connections with paid positions

Correlated	Direction	Correlation Coefficient (Spearman)	p-level
Paid directors / supervisors \leftrightarrow Use of equity as funding source	Negative	-0.294 / -0.227	0.99 / 0.95
No paid positions \leftrightarrow Use of equity as funding source	Positive	0.282	0.99
No paid positions \leftrightarrow Use of subordinated loans as funding source	Negative	-0.219	0.99

In addition to the correlations already discussed above, the SPSS correlation analysis produces some significant correlations between paid positions and other characteristics. An absence of paid positions is positively correlated with the use of equity as a funding source and negatively correlated with the use of subordinated loans. This may point to the additional administrative burden of such loans. By contrast, where directors and/or supervisors are paid, it is less likely that equity is used to finance a renewable energy project.

LEGAL FORM

Legal form	Number	Percentage (in %)
Genossenschaft (eG)	94	74
Combination eG and public limited-liability company (AG)	1	0.8
GbR	1	0.8

Combination GbR and eG	1	0.8
GmbH & Co. KG	5	3.9
Combination eG and GmbH & Co. KG	23	18.1
Combination GbR and GmbH & Co. KG	1	0.8
GmbH	1	0.8

FINANCING RENEWABLE ENERGY CAPACITY

N = 127

Source of funding	Average share in project finance (in %)	Standard deviation
Reserves of the community	22.65	26.193
Capital increases	31.66	31.153
Loan from banks or other institutional lenders	31.29	32.648
Subordinated loans from members	14.39	22.689
Crowd funding	0	0

Remarkable findings:

- 50 out of 127 respondents (39.4%) finance their projects without resort to loans from institutionalised lenders;
- 75 out of 127 respondents (59.1%) finance their projects without resort to subordinated loans from members;
- There are significant correlations between sources of funding. A use of equity strongly negatively correlates (coefficient: -0.344; $p = 0.99$) with a use of loans from banks, and the use of loans from banks strongly negatively (-0.384; $p = 0.99$) correlates with use of subordinated loans from members. The type of project, i.e., whether it is a wind or PV project, may be a moderating factor. Meanwhile, the use of equity does not seem to have a significant impact on the use of subordinated loans.

Purposes

Goal	Included in statute	Percentage included (in %)
Lower energy prices for members	15	11.8
Local economic activity or other economic benefits	32	25.2
Renewable energy and other environmental benefits	111	87.4
A stronger community life and/or other social benefits for the municipality or other surrounding communities	53	41.7
Disbursement of profits to the members	37	29.1
None of the above	4	3.1

Connections with purposes laid down in statutes

Correlated	Direction	Correlation Coefficient (Spearman)	p-level
Electricity fed into the grid \leftrightarrow environmental benefits as goal	Positive	0.263	0.99
Heat fed into a local grid \leftrightarrow environmental benefits as goal	Negative	-0.253	0.99
Year of foundation \leftrightarrow Social benefits as goals	The younger, the more likely.	0.378	0.99
Paid directors / supervisors \leftrightarrow Disbursement of profits as goal	Positive	0.414 / 0.182	0.99 / 0.95
No paid position \leftrightarrow Disbursement of profits as goal	Negative	-0.25	0.99
Medium-sized enterprises as members \leftrightarrow Disbursement as goal	Negative	-0.26	0.99
Representatives of authorities on the Board \leftrightarrow disbursement as goal	Negative	-0.317	0.99

The SPSS correlation analysis produces some significant correlations between the purposes laid down in the statutes and other aspects. Respondents that feed their electricity into the grid or supply it to specific buildings are more likely to set environmental benefits as a goal in their statute. By contrast, respondents with a local heat grid are less likely to include environmental benefits in their statutes. There is a connection between disbursement as a goal in the statute and the degree of professionalisation. Having paid directors or supervisors is positively correlated with disbursements as a goal in the statute, while energy communities with no paid positions are less likely to include that goal in their statutes. Younger energy communities are more likely to include social benefits in their statute. Interestingly, even the composition of the membership and the Board of Directors seems to have an impact on disbursement as a statutory goal. Representatives of authorities on the Board and medium-sized enterprises as members seem to make energy communities less likely to lay down the disbursement of profits as a goal in the statute.

Use of profits

DISBURSEMENT

Statistics: Percentage of net annual profit disbursed

N	Valid	124
	Missing	4
Average		30.45
Median		30.00
Standard Deviation		30.774

Interesting findings:

- 35 out of 124 respondents (28.2%) do not disburse any dividend.
- Positively correlated with **more members** (coefficient: 0.249, $p = 0.99$), **electricity supplied to buildings** (0.198, $p = 0.95$), **donations** (0.44, $p = 0.99$), and **use of equity** (0.236, $p = 0.99$) for project finance.
- Negatively correlated with **year of foundation** (-0.227, $p = 0.95$), meaning younger energy communities tend to disburse a lower percentage of the net annual profit.

DONATIONS TO GOOD CAUSES

Statistics: Percentage of net annual profit donated

N	Valid	124
	Missing	4
Average		2.76
Median		1.00
Standard deviation		12.910

Interesting findings:

- 56 out of 124 respondents (45.2%) do not donate to good causes;
- Two respondents donate all their profits to a good cause.
- Positively correlated with **PV installations** (coefficient: 0.256, $p = 0.99$), **supplying electricity to buildings** (0.209, $p = 0.95$), **more members** (0.193, $p = 0.95$), **use of equity** (0.194, $p = 0.95$), **subordinated loans** (0.228, $p = 0.95$), having a **day-to-day manager** (0.299, $p = 0.99$), and having more members from outside the district (0.271, $p = 0.99$).
- Negatively correlated with the **year of foundation** (-0.21, $p = 0.95$), **no paid positions** (-0.275, $p = 0.99$) and **use of bank loans** (-0.212, $p = 0.95$).

Minimum Investment

Statistics: Minimum amount payable for entry (in EUR)

N	Valid	124
	Missing	4
Average		764.34
Median		350.00
Standard deviation		1545.479

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulated Percent
Valid	5	1	,8	,8	,8
	50	2	1,6	1,6	2,4
	60	1	,8	,8	3,2
	75	1	,8	,8	4,0
	90	1	,8	,8	4,8
	100	34	26,6	27,4	32,3
	150	1	,8	,8	33,1
	200	5	3,9	4,0	37,1
	250	8	6,3	6,5	43,5
	263	2	1,6	1,6	45,2
	275	2	1,6	1,6	46,8
	300	4	3,1	3,2	50,0
	400	1	,8	,8	50,8
	500	34	26,6	27,4	78,2
	550	1	,8	,8	79,0
	600	1	,8	,8	79,8
	1000	13	10,2	10,5	90,3
	1060	1	,8	,8	91,1
	2000	2	1,6	1,6	92,7
	2012	1	,8	,8	93,5
3000	2	1,6	1,6	95,2	
5000	3	2,3	2,4	97,6	
6000	1	,8	,8	98,4	
10000	2	1,6	1,6	100,0	
	Total	124	96,9	100,0	
Missing	System	4	3,1		
	Total	128	100,0		

Connections with minimum investment

Correlated	Direction	Correlation Coefficient (Spearman)	p-level
PV	Negative	-0.192	0.95
Electricity fed into the grid	Negative	-0.231	0.99
Number of members	Negative	-0.242	0.99
Members residing outside the district of the RE installation	Negative	-0.24	0.99

The SPSS correlation analysis produces some significant correlations between the minimum investment and other aspects. The required amount payable upon entry is likely to be lower if the energy community uses solar power, feeds electricity into the grid, has more members, and/or more members residing outside the district. The reasons for these correlations may be that solar power projects are relatively cheaper and a higher number of members entails that each members has to contribute less. On the other hand, a lower minimum investment is also likely to attract more members.

Membership

EXCLUDED GROUPS OF LEGAL PERSONS (multiple answers possible)

Group	Number	Percentage of all respondents (in %)
Local public bodies	5	3.9
Other legal persons under public law / public authorities	11	8.7
Energy companies / utilities	12	9.4
Companies with 250 or more employees	8	6.3
Companies with 50 or more employees	6	4.7
None of these groups	106	83.5

Interesting findings:

- Energy communities that exclude one group of legal persons are likely to exclude others as well. For example, the exclusion of energy companies significantly positively correlates with the exclusion of local (coefficient: 0.627, $p = 0.99$) and non-local authorities (0.57, $p = 0.99$), large enterprises (0.63, $p = 0.99$) and of medium-sized enterprises (0.689, $p = 0.99$).
- There is a connection between professionalisation and the exclusion of different powerful legal persons, suggesting that professionalisation is a means to ensure the independence of the energy community:
 - paid directors are positively correlated with the exclusion of local authorities (0.237, $p = 0.99$), energy companies (0.219, $p = 0.95$), and large (0.264, $p = 0.99$) as well as medium-sized enterprises (0.201, $p = 0.95$).
 - having no paid positions negatively correlates with the exclusion of energy companies (-0.247, $p = 0.99$).

GROUNDS FOR NON-ADMISSION OR EXPULSION (multiple answers possible)

Ground	Number	Percentage of all respondents (in %)
Residence at a certain distance from the renewable energy installation(s)	51	40.2
Bankruptcy	92	72.4

Membership of a certain political party or other organisation	1	0.8
(Severe) Non-compliance with the rules of the community	112	88.2
Stake in an organisation that competes with the community on the energy market or in another respect	46	36.2

Interesting findings:

- A community that **feeds electricity into the public grid** is less likely to impose residence restrictions (coefficient: -0.2, p = 0.95), just as communities with **more medium-sized enterprises** among their members (0.212, p = 0.95)
- Expelling competitors is negatively correlated with the **feeding of electricity into the public grid** (-0.232, p = 0.99) and the **use of equity** in project finance (-0.296, p = 0.99). By contrast, communities that **feed heat into a local grid** are more likely to exclude competitors (0.284, p = 0.99).

REQUIREMENTS FOR EXIT (multiple answers possible)

Requirements	Number	Percentage of all respondents (in %)
Notice period	117	92.1
Partial or full relinquishment of the member's investment in the community	2	1.6

Decision-making

VOTES OF MEMBERS

Number of votes	Number	Percentage (in %)
One person, one vote	116	95.9
Up to three votes	1	0.8
More than three votes	4	3.3

Note:

- Under the German Cooperative Act (*Genossenschaftsgesetz*, GenG), the statute may assign up to three votes to a member, unless more than 75% of members are businesses or cooperatives (§ 43, sub-section 3, No. 1).
- Limited partnerships with a private limited-liability company (GmbH & Co. KG) have responded 'More than three votes'.

INFLUENCE OF CERTAIN GROUPS IN ASSEMBLY OF MEMBERS

1 = members with residence outside the district of the RE installation

2 = public authorities

3 = major lender

4 = large companies (> 250 employees)

5 = medium-sized companies (51-250 employees)

Statistics: share of votes

		1	2	3	4	5
N	Valid	119	119	119	119	118
	Missing	9	9	9	9	10
Average		9.34	2.02	2.76	0.47	4.14
Median		5.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.00
Standard deviation		16.348	9.422	15.812	1.982	6.543

Interesting findings:

- 96% of respondents indicate that members from outside the district do not hold more than 30% of the vote; 38% of respondents report no such members.
- Four respondents report that either an authority (one respondent) or a major lender (three respondents) holds all of the votes.
- Medium-sized companies never hold more than a third of the votes; large companies never more than 15%.

Connections with the composition of the members

Correlated	Direction	Correlation Coefficient (Spearman)	p-level
Members from outside ↔ Generation capacity	Positive	0.231	0.95
Members from outside ↔ Biomass	Negative	-0.232	0.95
Members from outside ↔ Electricity fed into public grid / supplied to buildings	Positive	0.261 / 0.218	0.99 / 0.95
Members from outside ↔ Heat fed into a local grid	Negative	-0.275	0.99
Members from outside ↔ Number of members	Positive	0.279	0.99
Members from outside ↔ Day-to-Day Manager	Positive	0.209	0.95
Members from outside ↔ No paid position	Negative	-0.303	0.99
Members from outside ↔ Members from outside on the Board	Positive	0.296	0.99
Major lenders as members ↔ Paid directors	Positive	0.253	0.99
Major lenders as members ↔ Representatives of major lenders on the Board	Positive	0.576	0.99
Major lenders as members ↔ Representatives of medium-sized enterprises on the Board	Negative	-0.188	0.95
Medium-sized enterprises as members ↔ Day-to-day manager	Positive	0.275	0.99
Medium-sized enterprises as members ↔ Use of equity	Positive	0.281	0.99
Medium-sized enterprises as members	Positive	0.288	0.99

↔ Representatives of medium-sized enterprises on the Board			
Medium-sized enterprises as members ↔ Public authorities as members	Positive	0.277	0.99

The SPSS correlation analysis produces some significant correlations between the composition of the members and other aspects. This paragraph summarises the main insights. It appears that communities using biomass and/or feeding their heat into the local grid tend to have fewer members residing outside their district. By contrast, communities that feed electricity into the public grid are more likely to have more members from outside the district. There also seems to be connection between the representation of certain groups and professionalisation. There is a positive correlation between medium-sized enterprises as members as well as members from outside the district and paid day-to-day managers and between major lenders as members and paid directors. This may suggest that these groups insist on professional management or are attracted by a professional organisation.

APPOINTMENT OF MANAGEMENT BOARD / BOARD OF DIRECTORS

By entity	Number	Percentage (in %)
Assembly of Members	24	18.9
Supervisory Board	95	74.8
Bank and local energy utility	1	0.8
Partner with unlimited liability	1	0.8
Family	1	0.8

REPRESENTATION OF GROUPS ON THE BOARD

1 = board member(s) outside the district of the RE installation

2 = public authorities

3 = major lender

4 = large companies (> 250 employees)

5 = medium-sized companies (51-250 employees)

Statistics: Percentage of seats on the board

		1	2	3	4	5
N	Valid	121	121	121	121	121
	Missing	7	7	7	7	7
Average		6,60	15,63	3,87	4,21	15,58
Median		,00	,00	,00	,00	,00
Standard deviation		19,429	22,451	16,170	13,685	22,167

Group	25-49%	≥ 50%
1	8 respondents	7
2	19	19
3	1	6
4	3	7
5	26	18
3+4+5	25	31

Connections with the composition of the Board

Correlated	Direction	Correlation Coefficient (Spearman)	p-level
Board members from outside the district ↔ Number of members	Negative	-0.234	0.99
Representatives of authority on the board ↔ Use of equity	Positive	0.429	0.99
Representatives of authority on the board ↔ Paid directors	Negative	-0.217	0.95
Representatives of authority on the board ↔ No paid positions	Positive	0.183	0.95
Representatives of major lenders on the board ↔ Paid directors	Positive	0.223	0.95
Representatives of large enterprises on the	Negative	-0.249	0.99

Board ↔ Day-to-day manager			
Representatives of medium-sized enterprises on the Board ↔ Day-to-day manager	Positive	0.191	0.95

The SPSS correlation analysis produces some significant correlations between the composition of the board and other aspects. There is a negative correlation between the representation of non-local members on the board and the number of members. This may be an indication that non-local members are more likely to obtain a seat on the board in smaller communities. Board members representing an authority are positively correlated with the use of equity when a renewable energy project is financed. Moreover, it appears that the representation of different groups is correlated in different ways with professionalisation. While board members representing an authority are positively correlated with no paid positions, representatives of medium-sized and larger enterprises and those of major lenders are positively correlated with a day-to-day manager and, respectively, paid directors.

SUPERVISION OF ASSEMBLY OF MEMBERS (multiple answers possible)

Body	Number	Percentage of all respondents (in %)
Board of Directors	14	11
Supervisory Board	23	18.1
Association of cooperatives	10	7.9
None	89	70.1

SUPERVISION OF BOARD (multiple answers possible)

Body	Number	Percentage of all respondents (in %)
Assembly of Members	34	
Supervisory Board	117	
Association of cooperatives	7	
None	2	

Note:

- Two respondents who report no control at all are a civil-law partnership ('GbR', *Gesellschaft bürgerlichen Rechts*) and a community with no legal form.
- The German Cooperative Act provides for a Supervisory Board (§ 9, sub-section 1). The Supervisory Board can be omitted if the cooperative has fewer than 20 members.

SUPERVISORY MEANS (multiple answers possible)

Means	Number	Percentage of all respondents (in %)
Right to overturn the decision	27	21.3
Right to dismiss the decision-making body	107	84.3
Right to bring judicial action for annulment of the decision	19	15
None	5	3.9

Skills

OF BOARD AND ACTIVE MEMBERS (multiple answers possible)

Skill	Number	Percentage of all respondents (in %)
Energy regulation	21	16.5
Technological aspects of the energy grid	32	25.2
Contracting	47	37
Accounting and tax	51	40.2
Finance	60	47.2
Internal and external communication	55	43.3
Project management	73	57.5
Management of organisations	108	85
Technological aspects of relevant renewable energy installations	87	68.5
Manual skills	63	49.6
None of the above	1	0.8

➤ **Skill profiles: Combinations of skills**

Statistics: Number of combined areas of expertise and skills

N	Valid	119
	Missing	9
Average		5.0168
Median		4.0000
Standard deviation		2.43903

		Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulated Percent
Valid	,00	1	,8	,8
	1,00	1	,8	1,7
	2,00	12	10,1	11,8
	3,00	24	20,2	31,9
	4,00	24	20,2	52,1
	5,00	17	14,3	66,4
	6,00	9	7,6	73,9
	7,00	6	5,0	79,0
	8,00	9	7,6	86,6
	9,00	9	7,6	94,1
	10,00	7	5,9	100,0
	Total		119	100,0
Missing	System	9		
Total		128		

➤ *Disregarding knowledge on energy regulation and grids*

Statistics: Number of combined areas of expertise and skills

N	Valid	119
	Missing	9
Average		4.5714
Median		4.0000
Standard deviation		1.93790

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulated Percent
Valid	,00	1	,8	,8	,8
	1,00	2	1,6	1,7	2,5
	2,00	11	8,6	9,2	11,8
	3,00	25	19,5	21,0	32,8
	4,00	27	21,1	22,7	55,5
	5,00	21	16,4	17,6	73,1
	6,00	7	5,5	5,9	79,0
	7,00	10	7,8	8,4	87,4
	8,00	15	11,7	12,6	100,0
	Total	119	93,0	100,0	
Missing	System	9	7,0		
Total		128	100,0		

SKILLS OF HIRED PERSONNEL OR EXTERNALS (multiple answers possible)

Skill	Number	Percentage of all respondents (in %)
Energy regulation	16	12.6
Technological aspects of the energy grid	23	18.1
Contracting	82	64.6
Accounting and tax	102	80.3
Finance	74	58.3
Internal and external communication	7	5.5
Project management	39	30.7
Management of organisations	8	6.3
Technological aspects of relevant renewable energy installations	52	40.9
Manual skills	89	70.1
None of the above	5	3.9

AGGREGATED: ACTIVE MEMBERS, HIRED PERSONNEL AND EXTERNALS

Skill	Number	Percentage of all respondents (in %)
Energy regulation	33	26
Technological aspects of the energy grid	47	37
Contracting	109	85.8
Accounting and tax	117	92.1
Finance	110	86.6
Internal and external communication	62	48.8
Project management	98	77.2
Management of organisations	110	86.6
Technological aspects of relevant renewable energy installations	110	86.6
Manual skills	113	89

COMPLETE SKILL SETS

Statistics: Skills and areas of expertise of active members, personnel externals combined

N	Valid	118
	Missing	10
Average		7.7034
Median		8.0000
Standard deviation		1.50389

		Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulated Percent
Valid	3,00	1	,8	,8
	4,00	2	1,7	2,5
	5,00	3	2,5	5,1
	6,00	16	13,6	18,6

	7,00	34	28,8	47,5
	8,00	29	24,6	72,0
	9,00	13	11,0	83,1
	10,00	20	16,9	100,0
	Total	118	100,0	
Missing	System	10		
Total		128		

➤ *Disregarding knowledge on energy regulation and grids:*

Statistics: Skills and expertise of active members, personnel and external combined

N	Valid	118
	Missing	10
Average		7.0254
Median		7.0000
Standard deviation		1.08180

		Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulated Percent
Valid	3,00	1	,8	,8
	4,00	2	1,7	2,5
	5,00	8	6,8	9,3
	6,00	21	17,8	27,1
	7,00	36	30,5	57,6
	8,00	50	42,4	100,0
	Valid	118	100,0	
Missing	System	10		
Total		128		